

Karyotypic Studies on Four Species of Staphylinidae (Coleoptera : Polyphaga)

Paper Id : 20665 Submission Date : 2025-08-11 Acceptance Date : 2025-08-20 Publication Date : 2025-08-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18066231

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Abstract	Karyological investigations were carried out on adult male individuals of four species of Staphylinidae beetles viz. <i>Eulissus anachoreta</i> Er., <i>Metolinus leucoconemis</i> Kr., <i>Gauropterus fulgidus</i> F., and <i>Xantholinus metallicus</i> Fauv. <i>E. anachoreta</i> Er. and <i>M. leucoconemis</i> Kr., possesses $2n = 28 : 13 + Xy_p$, <i>G. fulgidus</i> F. Possesses $2n = 34 : 16 + Xy_p$ whereas <i>X. metallicus</i> Fauv. exhibited $2n = 42 : 20 + Xy_p$. Mitosis and meiosis have been described and discussed.
Keywords	Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Karyotype, Autosome, Sex Chromosome Mechanism.
Introduction	The family Staphylinidae is one of the most interesting and the largest family of Coleoptera comprising about 45,000 species and probably over 75% of tropical species are still undescribed (Howard et al., 1998). Its subfamily Staphylininae consists of species collectively called true rove beetles. Most of the beetles of this subfamily feed exclusively on dung. Most of them feed on vertebrate (mostly mammalian) dung, but there are also species specialized on carrion, fungi, rotting fruit and other decomposing plant material. Keeping in view the economic importance and paucity of literature on chromosomes of this group the present investigations on the chromosomes of four species belonging to four genera were under taken. All species are new addition to the cytology of this group.
Objective of study	The present study aims to investigate the karyological features of four rove beetle species - <i>Eulissus anachoreta</i> , <i>Metolinus leucoconemis</i> , <i>Gauropterus fulgidus</i> , and <i>Xantholinus metallicus</i> - belonging to the family Staphylinidae. By analyzing mitotic and meiotic stages in adult males, the study focuses on determining chromosome number, structure, and sex-chromosome mechanisms, with the goal of contributing to the cytotaxonomy and evolutionary understanding of this under-studied beetle group.
Review of Literature	<p>The family Staphylinidae is the largest and one of the most diverse families of beetles, with over 45,000 described species and many more yet to be documented, particularly in tropical regions (Howard et al., 1998). Early cytogenetic studies (Stevens, 1906; Smith, 1950, 1953; Mickey & Park, 1956; Vidal, 1984; Yoshida, 1952) have shown that species of this family display considerable variation in chromosome numbers ($2n = 18$ to $2n = 56$). Yadav et al. (1994) and Chand (1989) extended this knowledge in Indian rove beetles, revealing diverse karyotypes and consistent Xy_p sex-chromosome systems.</p> <p><i>Paederus littoralis</i> exhibits a diploid number of $2n=32$, aiding taxonomic resolution within Staphylinidae (Bhatti & Khajuria, 2018). <i>Philonthus cognatus</i> genome from the Staphylinidae family has been sequenced and annotated (Crowley et al., 2023).</p> <p>Despite these efforts, only a limited number of Staphylinid species have been analyzed cytogenetically. The present investigation addresses this gap by reporting four additional species of Staphylinidae, each studied cytologically for the first time.</p>
Methodology	Adult male individuals of four species belonging to four genera <i>Eulissus anachoreta</i> Er., <i>Metolinus leucoconemis</i> Kr., <i>Gauropterus fulgidus</i> F. and <i>Xantholinus metallicus</i> Fauv. constituted the materials for the present investigations. All the beetles were collected under the mercury vapour lamps during February to April 2024-2025 from Ratlam (Madhya Pradesh). Chromosome preparations were made following Yadav and Lyapunova (1983).
Result and Discussion	<i>Eulissus anachoreta</i> Er. The diploid number of 28 chromosomes was revealed by spermatogonial metaphase (Fig.01).

In the karyotype seven autosome pairs 1-3,7,9,10 and 11 are metacentric, pair 4-6,8,12, and 13 are submetacentric, remaining sex chromosomes X and y are also submetacentric (Fig.02).

13 dumb-bell shaped autosomal bivalents and the sex bivalent Xy_p constituted the metaphase I plate (Fig.09).

The first reductional division result in the formation of metaphase II plates (Fig.10).

The male chromosome formula is $13AA+Xy_p$.

Metolinus leuconemis Kr. Spermatogonial metaphase revealed the diploid number of 28 chromosomes (Fig.03).

In the karyotype chromosome pairs 1,3,4,6,7,9,10 and 11, are metacentric, pair 2, 5,8,12 and 13 are submetacentric and sex chromosomes X and y are acrocentric (Fig.04).

Metaphase I revealed 13 dumb-bell shaped autosomal bivalents (Fig.11).

The reductional division results in the formation of one type of metaphase II plates with X chromosome (Fig. 12).

The male chromosome formula is $13AA+Xy_p$.

Gauropterus fulgidus F. The diploid compliment of 34 chromosomes was exhibited by spermatogonial metaphase (fig.05).

The karyotype comprises ten pairs of metacentric (pair 1-10), five pairs of submetacentric (pairs 11-15) and one pair of acrocentric autosome (pair 16), the sex chromosomes X and y are also acrocentric (fig.06).

Metaphase I revealed 13 dumbbell shaped autosomal bivalent and the sex bivalent Xy_p (fig.13).

The reductional division results in the formation of one type of metaphase II plates with X chromosome (Fig. 14).

The male chromosome formula is $16AA+Xy_p$.

Xantholinus metallicus Fauv. The diploid number of 42 chromosomes was revealed by spermatogonial metaphase (Fig. 07)

in the karyotype 10 pairs of autosomes 1- 3, 6, 8- 11, 16 and 18 are metacentric. Pairs 4, 5, 7, 12-15, 17, 19 and 20 are submetacentric and sex chromosomes X and y are acrocentric (Fig.08).

Metaphase I revealed 20 rod shaped autosomal bivalents and the sex bivalent Xy_p (Fig.15) The reductional division result in the formation of metaphase II plates one with y chromosome and the other with X chromosome (Fig.16).

The male chromosome formula is $20AA+Xy_p$.

Staphylinidae is known on cytological grounds by 73 species (Chand 1989, Mickey and Park 1956, Smith 1950, 1953, Stevens 1906, 1909, Vidal 1984, Vorontsov et al. 1984, Yadav et al. 1987, Yoshida 1952 and present report). Overall Staphylinidae exhibit a wide spectrum of Karyotype. In spite of the limited number of cytotaxonomically studies species, this group exhibits variation in the diploid number from $2n = 18$ to $2n = 56$ (Yadav et al. 1994). All species of beetles exhibited parachute sex chromosome (Xy_p) during the present investigations. Wider Karyological research is needed to obtain a clearer insight into the taxonomic and evolutionary relationship among whole family. During the course of present investigation of the four species the total chromosome length was found to be maximum in *Xantholinus metallicus* Fauv. (37.28μ) and minimum in *Metolinus leuconemis* Kr. (30.69μ). All chromosomes show a gradual decrease in size. The size of X chromosome smallest in *X. metallicus* Fauv. (0.64μ) and largest in *M. leuconemis* Kr. (1.39μ). *Eulissus anachoreta* Er. has the largest y (0.93μ) whereas y was smallest in *X. metallicus* Fauv. (0.13μ).

Comparative study of the karyotypes of beetles is presented in Table 1

Table 1 : Karyotype analysis of four species of Staphylinidae beetles.

Sr. Species No.	Chromosome pairs in percentage length																				Length in μ				
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	X	Y	TCL	X	Y
1 <i>Eulissus anachoreta</i> Er.	15.7	14	13.8	13.6	13.4	13	12.8	12.4	11.66	11.2	10.1	9.5	7.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5.35	4.44	35.25	1.12	0.93
2 <i>Melolinus leucoconemis</i> Vz.	13.1	12.9	12.3	11.2	10.45	10.3	10	9.8	9.2	9	8.75	8.55	8.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.65	5.9	30.69	1.39	0.29
3 <i>Gauropterus fulgidus</i> F.	12.4	12.2	11.9	11.75	11.45	10.9	10.8	10.45	10.3	9.9	8.2	7.35	7.25	6.81	6.45	5.3	-	-	-	-	4	3.2	32.15	0.83	0.17
4 <i>Xantholinus metallicus</i> Fav.	12	11.8	11.6	11.45	10.35	10.3	10.25	10.2	9.7	9.4	9	8.9	8.6	8.4	7	6.7	5.5	4.2	3.88	3.3	3.1	2.2	37.28	0.84	0.13

TCL = Total chromosome length.

Conclusion

The karyotypic analysis of four species of Staphylinidae reveals distinct chromosomal profiles. Diploid numbers varied from $2n = 28$ in *E. anachoreta* and *M. leucoconemis*, to $2n = 34$ in *G. fulgidus*, and up to $2n = 42$ in *X. metallicus*. All species exhibited the Xy_p (parachute type) sex-chromosome mechanism, typical for beetles. Differences in centromere position and chromosome size suggest species-specific karyotype evolution.

This study not only adds new cytogenetic records for the family but also reinforces the value of karyological data in taxonomic differentiation and evolutionary inference within Coleoptera. Further studies on more species are essential for broader cytotaxonomic frameworks.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to the Head Department of Zoology, P.M. College of Excellence, Govt. P. G. Arts and Science College, Ratlam for providing the necessary laboratory facilities and Dr. Neena Chouhan, forest Entomologist FRI, Dehradun for their help in identification of beetles.

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